

mosaic

MOSAIC co-creation methodology toolkit

Section 2: Stakeholder mapping and
recruiting

Authors: Marzia Mazzonetto, Maria Zolotonosa , Carmen Fenollosa, Fabien Lambert (Stickydot srl); Angela Simone, Anna Pellizzone, Federica Manzoli (Bassetti Foundation).

07/11/2023

Mission-Oriented Swafs to Advance Innovation through Co-creation

Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under
Grant Agreement No. 101006382 - H2020-SwafS-2018-2020 / H2020-SwafS-2020-1

This project has received funding from the European Union's

Table of Contents

1. Stakeholder mapping guidelines	3
2. Example of stakeholder recruitment open call.....	4

1. Stakeholder mapping guidelines

Stakeholder mapping is a tool used to identify and analyze their stakeholders. In this process, stakeholders are individuals or groups that have an interest in or are affected by the chosen challenge. In the MOSAIC co-creation process we involve stakeholders from the « quadruple helix », meaning representatives from the public sector, academia, the private sector and civil society.

The purpose of stakeholder mapping is to think about all possible type of stakeholders that have a stake in the chosen challenge, even indirectly. The stakeholder mapping can then be used to identify participants to invite to the Gathering and following activities.

Stakeholder mapping typically involves creating a visual representation of the stakeholders and their relationships to the challenge. This can be done using a variety of tools, such as a matrix or a spider diagram. The mapping process should be iterative and eventually involve feedback from stakeholders to ensure that no relevant participants are left behind.

Below is an example of the stakeholder mapping conducted on Mural (online) with representatives of the city of Gothenburg, around the challenge of making mobility in the city more sustainable.

Beside synchronous exercises, asynchronous tools can also be prepared (e.g., online shared documents), in order to further integrate mapping.

2. Example of stakeholder recruitment open call

Towards sustainable mobility in Gothenburg

(This is the text of the call that was published to launch the co-creation process in Gothenburg. It was published on the city website and promoted through several channels, including social media, local radios, etc.).

Göteborg is on the path to becoming Carbon neutral by 2030. However, to do so it needs for all of us to work together to devise solutions that are efficient and functional for everyone. The way we move around has a great impact on the carbon emissions of our cities. At the same time, mobility shapes our lifestyles, our comfort, and the choices we make every day. Decreasing emissions generated by urban mobility will affect our lifestyle and will require close collaboration towards creative solutions.

Göteborgs Stad is inviting participants to this collaborative open innovation programme aimed at creating new partnerships to design shared solutions. The goal is to come up with creative ideas to reducing carbon emissions while addressing citizens' needs regarding the way they move around.

The context

The most recent IPCC report is clear about the dangers posed by the climate crisis and the need to act. Cities need to play a pivotal role in achieving climate neutrality. Although they take up only 4% of the EU's land area, cities are home to 75% of EU citizens, 65% of the world's energy consumption and account for more than 70% of global CO2 emission. Urban mobility accounts for 40 % of all CO2 emissions from road transport and up to 70% of other pollutants from transport.

We want to be able to reach climate neutrality by 2030, therefore, we must achieve an unprecedented transition, making a great effort to transform our cities.

Gothenburg, alongside 111 other European cities, has committed to becoming climate-neutral, and the city's new environmental and climate programme aims to reduce its climate impact to "close to zero" by 2030, with a view to reaching a zero footprint as quickly as possible. This means that Gothenburg will need to reduce emissions in its geographical area by at least 10.3% per year and consumption-based emissions by at least 7.6% per year.

The challenge we invite you to address

The transition to sustainable urban mobility is generally acknowledged as one of the major challenges for the future. With an urban area with around 1 million inhabitants and only 570.000 city dwellers, Gothenburg needs to ensure the mobility of a big number of commuters. The main question we will focus on is:

How can we co-develop inclusive mobility that meets personal needs, is affordable, comfortable and reliable?

The process

Our goal is to develop solutions with and for citizens, local businesses and public representatives to support sustainable changes to the way we move around the city. We need solutions where the different players understand each other's preferences and priorities by

working together along the same journey. Successful collaboration will increase our potential to develop creative solutions, think laterally and experiment with “out of the box” ideas.

Together, we will find concrete solutions to questions such as:

- What would make our life better mobility-wise?
- What could fit your mobility needs, while also decreasing your carbon footprint?
- What would improve the user-friendliness and aesthetics of mobility in the neighbourhood?

The first step in the process will be the gathering, where all selected participants will get the chance to meet, get to know each other and form co-creation teams. This event takes place during (... - add dates of the Gathering).

All participants need to be available for those two half-days. For the whole process participants should be available to take part in (...) meetings until (...) and work with their teams in between on developing their projects. None of the co-creation activities will require a full-day commitment, they will have a duration of between one and four hours and will be organised at a time that is suitable for most.

Who can apply?

- NGOs / Non-profit organisations
- Citizens, civic organisations, communities
- Research Organisations/Academia
- Industrial/Innovation Companies
- Start-up / SME / Social enterprises
- Public/governmental organisation

All applicants are welcome and we invite actors with different backgrounds: companies, start-ups, researchers from all fields, citizens/community groups, neighbour's associations, commuters, social entrepreneurs, engineers, designers, economists, fleet managers, environmental NGOs, shop owners, anyone with mobility wishes and needs willing to be part of this change.

The co-creation process will focus on the south-west commuter belt of Gothenburg. We particularly invite participants who for any reasons frequently use the road 158 from Järnbrottsmotet until Brottkärrsmotet, which is the focus area for the co-creation process. If you feel you have any kind of direct or indirect experience on this area, even if not directly connected to it, please apply.

Selection criteria

We expect to involve around 50 individuals including organisation representatives in the process. In case a selection will be needed, we will choose participants based on ensuring a fair balance of:

- Representatives of the above-mentioned categories.
- Know-how and views represented.
- Motivations and interest in the topic.
- Willingness to work in a partnership and to collaborate with others.

Benefits/What's in it for me?

- Let your ideas be part of the ongoing work towards a climate neutral city by 2030.
- Improve mobility services in your city.
- Meet new people and build impactful collaborations.
- Make your voices, views and needs heard.
- Access to a group of international open innovation experts.
- Learn complementary approaches and skills.
- And above all, contribute to making your community a healthier place to live.

The 3 best collaborative projects that will emerge will be offered technical and operational support for up to 6 months to help develop and prototype their ideas (multi-stakeholder coordination, design thinking, intellectual property, project management, fundraising, etc.). The 3 best projects will also be shown how to build clear visions of how their proposed solutions will scale and contribute to solving the challenge – an essential element for mobilising further support from the city.

Commitment

The city of Gothenburg is the initiator of this programme. It is being supported by the EU-funded MOSAIC project and in particular its coordinator, Stickydot srl, a Brussels-based collective that shapes research and innovation through multi-stakeholder engagement and co-creation.

The city administration shares the objective and commits to supporting the programme. It will both take part in the process and closely follow each of the projects being developed by the three selected teams. It will assess all projects in terms of scalability, innovation, effectiveness and implementation. Since the result is created by local stakeholders the city of Gothenburg will value the results highly. Each result will be considered for further financial support or assisted into the decision-making process of the city.

Application form

1. Name and contact details.
2. Describe who you are, and in case you have an affiliation, your organisation.
3. What motivates you to take part in this programme?
4. Describe your know-how and/or daily life experience in the field of mobility and what you could bring to the challenge we are trying to solve. (Know-how does not mean that one needs to be an expert in the topic, e.g. if you are from a Neighbour's association in a certain area, you have expertise in the local area: its lifestyle, the habits, the problems, etc.).
5. Do you have any existing project idea in the field of mobility? If so describe.
6. What do you think you can benefit from collaborating and building partnerships with others?
7. Are you available to attend the first meeting, called the Gathering) on (...)?